

An Analysis of Specialized Sports-Related Anglicisms: Their Use in the European Spanish Press Nowadays

Uma análise de anglicismos especializados relacionados ao esporte: seu uso na imprensa espanhola europeia na atualidade

Carmen Luján-García

Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Las Palmas de Gran Canaria / España

carmen.lujan@ulpgc.es

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7050-777X>

Eugenia Esperanza Núñez Nogueroles

Universidad de Extremadura (UEx), Cáceres / España

eugenia@unex.es

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0540-4242>

Abstract: The aim of this study is to provide updated evidence of the use of non-adapted, adapted and false sports-related anglicisms in the European Spanish press. Specifically, this piece of research attempts to unveil technical/semi-technical English borrowings and to explore the pragmatic functions of these English lexical units in the current digital Spanish newswire. The method consisted of examining eight different media by using the constantly updating database of anglicisms ‘Observatorio Lázaro’ throughout a period of 9 months. A sample of 130 English lexical items was collected and subjected to an in-depth qualitative and descriptive analysis. Each borrowing was looked up in DAD –the most recent dictionary of sports-related English lexical items in Spanish– and was illustrated by a real example of its use in context excerpted from present-day Spanish newspapers. Terminology associated to a broad spectrum of specific sports –such as golf, basketball, rugby, cycling, etc.– was delved into. Results show that, while some terms have no connection to the rest of borrowings, many of them can be grouped according to certain parameters. Considering pragmatic functions, the use of some anglicisms proved not to be random but to respond to news reporters’ and journalists’ purposes. The study concludes that the pervasive influence exerted by English on Spanish concerning technical/semi-technical sports anglicisms remains in full force and effect nowadays, as this impact affects the vocabulary of a wide variety of sports games and exercises.

Keywords: sports; anglicisms; technical/semi-technical vocabulary; European Spanish; press.

Resumo: O objetivo deste estudo é fornecer evidências atualizadas do uso de anglicismos não adaptados, adaptados e falsos relacionados ao esporte na imprensa espanhola europeia. Especificamente, esta pesquisa tenta revelar palavras emprestadas do inglês técnico/semi-técnico e explorar as funções pragmáticas dessas unidades lexicais do inglês no atual jornalismo digital espanhol. O método de pesquisa consistiu em examinar oito mídias diferentes usando o banco de dados de anglicismos em constante atualização ‘Observatorio Lázaro’ ao longo de um período de 9 meses. Uma amostra de 130 itens lexicais em inglês foi coletada e submetida a uma análise qualitativa e descritiva aprofundada. Cada empréstimo foi consultado no DAD –o mais recente dicionário de anglicismos relacionados ao esporte em espanhol– e foi ilustrado por um exemplo real de seu uso no contexto extraído de jornais espanhóis atuais. Aprofundou-se a terminologia associada a um amplo espectro de esportes específicos – como golfe, basquete, rugby, ciclismo, etc. –. Os resultados mostram que, embora alguns termos não tenham conexão com o restante dos estrangeirismos, muitos deles podem ser agrupados de acordo com determinados parâmetros. Considerando as funções pragmáticas, o uso dos anglicismos mostrou-se não aleatório e sim uma resposta aos propósitos dos repórteres e jornalistas. O estudo conclui que a influência generalizada exercida pelo inglês sobre o espanhol nos anglicismos esportivos técnicos/semi-técnicos permanece em pleno vigor e efeito nos dias de hoje, pois esse impacto afeta o vocabulário de uma ampla variedade de jogos e exercícios esportivos.

Palavras-chave: esportes; anglicismos; vocabulário técnico/semi-técnico; espanhol europeu; imprensa.

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1 Introduction

A vast volume of literature has dealt with the growing tendency to use English lexical items to refer to a number of domains in Spanish (Balteiro; Campos, 2012; Bolaños-Medina; López Zurita, 2005; Luján-García, 2010; Luján-García; Pulcini, 2018; Bolaños-Medina; Luján-García, 2010; Orts Llopis; Almela Sánchez-Lafuente, 2012; among many others). The field of sports is not exceptional due to various reasons. Sports, like most other areas, is constantly exposed to the invasive influence of Anglo-American culture, and consequently English. In addition, it is a

fact that many of current sports have originally emerged in the UK or the US (Vázquez Amador *et al.*, 2015). As Rodríguez González and Castañón Rodríguez (2021) assert in their *Diccionario de Anglicismos del Deporte* (henceforth, DAD), the language of sports has its own features. On the one hand, it contains a technical set of terms that refer to some specialties and are far from the common use of the language. For example, a golf player or a windsurfer may use a kind of specialized, technical jargon when they refer to the sports they practice. But, on the other hand, some sports such as football or boxing have become so popular that the terminology used in them could be considered “semi-technical”. These authors also highlight the current constant emergence of new sports and the urgency and univocity imposed by the cultural globalization. Additionally, the speed of our communications make English the lingua franca necessary to respond to these communicative necessities. Indeed, authors dealing with different varieties of the Spanish language have identified sports as the field where anglicisms appear more frequently: Sánchez Fajardo’s (2016) study on Cuban Spanish and Núñez Nogueroles’s (2017) analysis of the European variety point in this direction.

Several pieces of research have provided deep account of the pervasive presence of English in the Spanish language of sports, adopting a broad perspective or focusing on specific subfields (football, boxing, surfing, etc.). From a general point of view, Torredadella-Flix and Nomdedeu-Rull (2013) as well as Rodríguez González (2012) brought attention to the fact that this influence began in the 19th century. Scholars such as Nomdedeu Rull (2019) highlight the first football English loanwords in Spanish since the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th century. With the focus on a more recent period, Vázquez Amador *et al.* (2015) have reported on the use of anglicisms in the Spanish press in the 1950s by comparing the edition of three different newspapers from Mexico, Argentina and Spain, respectively. In another piece of research, these scholars (Vázquez Amador; Lario de Oñate, 2015) provided evidence of the remarkable use of English lexical items in one sports newspaper, *Mundo Deportivo*, making a contrastive analysis between terms used in two different periods: 1906-1910 and 2010. These scholars concluded that the number of anglicisms not only has increased considerably throughout the last century, but it has also widened its spectrum of use. Moreover, as Oliva Marañón (2012) pointed out, a step further must be underlined: on some occasions, Spanish

derivatives have been created from English loanwords (an illustrative example presented by this scholar is the case of *goal* > *golear*, *goleada*, *goleador*, *golazo*, *hombre-gol*).

Balteiro (2011) extracted a total of 428 sports-related anglicisms from the *Nuevo Diccionario de Anglicismos* (NDA). She studied which ones were collected by other linguistic databases such as *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual* (CREA) and *Diccionario de la Lengua Española* (DLE), and also the different processes of adaptation undergone by many of these terms.

With respect to the jargon of boxing, Ayuso Collantes (2018) examined two different Spanish sports newspapers and found out that it was in the third part of the 20th century when a considerable number of English words were introduced in the Spanish language.

Considering lexical creativity, Guerrero Salazar (2018) delved into the usage of stylistic neologisms in the headlines of sports news. This author analyzed coinages created by means of foreign compounding elements, two of which being Eng. *-gate* ('scandal') and Germ. *-landia* ('fantastic place', 'fantastic world') – which entered Spanish through English. The figurative language plays an important role in the use of English lexical units, and Rodríguez González (2016) put the focus upon the metaphorical uses of anglicisms belonging to the area of sports –specifically to the football lexis– in other spheres such as politics, economics or the commercial domain.

For his part, Campos-Pardillos (2015) explored the use of false anglicisms in the field object of this study –sports– in Spanish and concluded that the attractiveness of these false anglicisms lies in the fact that they *look* English, with its implications of currently being a language of fashion and prestige. In this respect, it is noteworthy that some of these pseudo-anglicisms have been coined in French and it is from this language that they have entered Spanish (Gillain Muñoz, 2014).

Beyond the lexical level, the foreign influence has affected syntax too. In his study on sports news in Spanish at the beginning of the 21st century, Gillain Muñoz (2014) made reference to the effort that has been made to improve the quality of the written production in this specialized field, mentioning the role played by lexicographical works such as the *Diccionario panhispánico de dudas* (2005) in the search for alternatives to syntactic constructions characterized by their foreign flavor.

Other recipient languages have also become the object of study in several pieces of research. Bernard-Béziade and Attali (2009) analyzed the usage of anglicisms in the domain of football in French and they underlined that “the contribution of numerous English lexical units to the lexicon of other languages in touch with United Kingdom participates in the diffusion of sport and its level of penetration in geographical spaces” (p. 2219). In relation to surfing, Granvik (2019) carried out an exploratory analysis on the influence of the English vocabulary on surf talk in two Romance languages –Portuguese and Spanish–, finding out that there are more similarities than differences when it comes to this specialized lexicon in the tongues under study.

Considering the main factors that play a role in explaining the propensity of a language to being influenced by English, Bergh and Ohlander (2012, 2017) suggested, in their pieces of research on the acquisition of football lexis by different European tongues, that language attitudes as well as sociocultural and historical circumstances seem to carry more weight than purely linguistic reasons such as linguistic similarity or relatedness.

All these studies point out the importance that the use of anglicisms in the realm of sports has gained in Spanish throughout the last century, and especially throughout the last decades. Thus, it turns out to be necessary for this research area to monitor the influence exerted by English on the terminology employed in Spanish in this sphere. This study not only aims at providing updated data on this extensively examined field, but it also intends to offer an alternative view of sports anglicisms. It questions and discusses the degree of specialization of this terminology, addressing other aspects such as the categorization of these English terms, and provides a brief analysis of some of the pragmatic functions fulfilled by some of the compiled English lexical items.

2 Methodology

The collection of English lexical units gathered for this study was extracted by using the linguistic search tool of anglicisms called “Observatorio Lázaro” (Álvarez Mellado, 2020a, 2020c), which daily examines eight different Spanish written media: seven newspapers –*El Mundo*, *El Confidencial*, *ABC*, *El País*, *elDiario.es*, *20 minutos* and *La Vanguardia*– as well as the news agency EFE. This search tool –freely

available at <https://observatoriolazaro.es/>– contains a database with the anglicisms found in these media. The reason to choose this automatic extractor is that it provides quite updated data, which was the goal of our piece of research. The lexical material for this study was excerpted during the month of March of 2021, and it focused on data from the last semester of 2020 and the first trimester of 2021. Out of the great number of anglicisms collected alphabetically in the section “Lexicon” of this website, those terms belonging to the sphere of sports and characterized by their technical/ semitechnical nature were manually singled out. This process of selection was complex and difficult, since the researchers had to check the specific contexts in which each term was used, whether it was merely employed in sports – in one particular sport or in several ones– or whether the word was also used in other contexts different from the sports one.

Once the sample was built, each lexical unit was looked up in DAD, the most recent dictionary of sports-related anglicisms in Spanish – which has the advantage of being an updated compilation, since it was published in 2021. Furthermore, the terms have been presented in context to illustrate their usage. The definitions of the examined words have been taken from various well-known dictionaries: *Collins Dictionary* (CD), *Cambridge Online Dictionary* (COD), *MacMillan Dictionary* (MD) and *Oxford English Dictionary* (OED).

The analysis concentrates mostly on non-adapted anglicisms, with just some cases of two other types of borrowing: adapted and false anglicisms. A total number of 130 anglicisms has been examined, and a classification of these direct lexical borrowings (Pulcini *et al.*, 2012) into non-adapted, adapted, and false anglicisms has been carried out, as shown in the next section. Pulcini *et al.* (2012) divide lexical borrowings into direct and indirect and, within the direct ones, they distinguish among loanwords (which can be either non-adapted or adapted), false lexical borrowings and hybrid lexical borrowings. The reason to choose this instead of any other taxonomy is due to the fact that it covers the types of anglicisms analyzed in the present study and that it is the more adapted to the current nature of anglicisms in Spanish.

Since this paper aims at examining mainly non-adapted anglicisms, the tool ‘Observatorio Lázaro’, which searches and compiles merely those lexical units whose orthographic and morphological forms correspond to that of an English word (Álvarez Mellado, 2020b), is an appropriate resource for this study. Furthermore, non-adapted anglicisms

constitute the most numerous type of English loans in the area of sports in Spanish; as Balteiro's results prove,

the Spanish sports jargon mainly welcomes those foreign elements from English, which tend to remain unaltered; in fact, out of 381 true Anglicisms in the sample, 249 (65.35% of the Anglicisms, that is, 58.17% of the total number of items) were left in their original English form (Balteiro, 2011, p. 33).

Thus, by using as source the tool 'Observatorio Lázaro', which collects constantly updated data, we will be able to analyze the present-day state of non-adapted English borrowings, monitoring this way the evolution of this type of sports anglicisms in Spanish.

3 Findings

This section deals with different aspects. Firstly, a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the sample collected considering different categories of anglicisms is carried out. For this aim, Pulcini et al.'s typology (2012, p. 6), specifically the part on direct lexical borrowings, –since this one covers the types pertinent to our study– has been followed.

Secondly, the whole sample of the anglicisms compiled are defined and documented with real examples excerpted from 'Observatorio Lázaro'. Despite being generalist rather than newspapers specialized in sports, the eight media from which this search tool extracts anglicisms employ such highly technical terms that are addressed to readers with an advanced knowledge in the specific sports covered in the texts.

Table 1 offers a breakdown of the frequency and types of anglicisms in the sample collected. In this section, firstly, we will discuss those few cases of adapted and false anglicisms. Then, some cases of non-adapted English borrowings will also be explained, and due to space constraints, the rest of the examined non-adapted English terms are placed in the Appendix, Table 2. In all of the examples extracted, the anglicisms have been kept as they are in the original source. It means that many of these terms are in italics, simple or double inverted commas, but some of them do not contain any marker.

Table 1 – Breakdown of different types of anglicisms

Type of anglicism	Adapted	False	Non-adapted	Total
Number of items	3 (2.31%)	7 (5.38%)	120 (92.31%)	130

Source: own elaboration.

3.1 Adapted anglicisms

Adapted anglicisms are words or multi-word units borrowed from the English language with orthographic, phonological and/or morphological integration into the structures of the recipient language (RL). Semantically, RL meaning is close to the source language (SL) meaning (Pulcini *et al.*, 2012, p. 7). The following three cases of this type of anglicisms have been found in this study:

Coastering (from Eng. *coasteering*) is “the sport of following a coastline by swimming, climbing, diving, and walking while wearing a wetsuit, a life jacket, and a helmet” (CD). It is not present in DAD.

- (1) El «coastering» es una práctica deportiva que aprovecha al máximo la orografía de las costas (*ABC*, 14/07/2020).

Down is a shortened form from English *pindown screen*. It is a pick set by a player above the free-throw line on a player below the free-throw line (<https://nba.nbcsports.com/2017/04/10/pindown-screen-video-breakdown-nba-glossary-offense-terms/>). It is present in DAD.

- (2) De nuevo en tercer down y con problemas, Mahomes encuentra a Travis Kelce pero el tight-end no consigue atrapar el balón cuando estaba en una situación idónea (*El Mundo*, 08/02/2021).

Speed ski (present in DAD with this form) is another shortened version, in this case of the English term *downhill speed ski*. Therefore, in Spanish, there is an adaptation of the original term, which can be defined as “a competitive skiing event in which racers (...) compete to achieve the fastest speed on a steep, straight, and meticulously prepared track” (<https://www.britannica.com/sports/speed-skiing>).

- (3) En la modalidad de esquí más rápido, speed ski, una mujer, Valentina Greggio, compitiendo con hombres, es la candidata a romper el récord de velocidad (*El País*, 07/03/2021).

3.2 False anglicisms

False anglicisms are those words or multi-word units in the RL made up of English lexical elements but unknown or used with a conspicuously different meaning in English (Pulcini *et al.* 2012, p. 7). In this piece of research, the number of anglicisms belonging to this type amounts to seven.

Paddle surf (not present in DAD) is *paddleboarding* or *SUP* (*Stand Up Paddleboarding*) in English. It is a sport in which you travel across water or ride on waves using a board, which you can sit or stand on, and sometimes paddle (COD).

- (4) A sus casi 60 años, el exdirigente estadounidense ha demostrado que se encuentra en plena forma y ha sido visto practicando ‘paddle surf’ en las aguas del Pacífico (*20 minutos*, 12/01/2021).

Car-cross (not present in DAD) is not used in English. It is a type of vehicle with one seat and a tubular chassis of small size, and with a protective cage to avoid overturning and with a bike engine of 600 c.c. (<https://www.maralbacircuit.com/que-es-un-carcross-kartcross/>).

- (5) disputará una docena de rallies en Letonia y Estonia y el Europeo de car-cross (*La Vanguardia*, 21/02/2021).

Fast bike (not present in DAD) is not employed in English; the most similar term in this language is *superbike*.

- (6) Suzuki presenta la tercera generación de la «fast bike» Hayabusa (*ABC*, 08/02/2021).

Start lap (not present in DAD) is a slow lap that racers make in motor racing before the race starts for warming up. However, the genuine form in English is *warm up lap*.

- (7) El granadino Valero, que completaba la ‘start lap’ en el puesto 20, lograba cuajar una sólida carrera... (*EFE*, 10/10/2020).

Sparring (present in DAD) is the derivative term from the verb *to spar* – “to practise fighting with someone” – in the subfield of boxing and wrestling (MD). This term is not used in football in English. However, in Spanish we can see this word in different contexts, even in politics.

- (8) con equipos locales como el Vélez-Málaga o el Algeciras, que sirven de sparring a los de alto nivel (*El País*, 19/02/2021).

Supercrack (not present in DAD) is not used in English to emphasize the word *crack* when referring to a distinguished sports person.

- (9) ¿Está el Barça en disposición de fichar a un supercrack mundial? Sobre todo si se fuera Messi (*20 minutos*, 10/02/2021).

The interesting combination *trampolines jumping* (not present in DAD) deserves detailed attention. It refers to training exercises that are performed in a trampoline. Although, at first sight, it could seem a hybrid anglicism – a multi-word unit which freely combines a RL element with an English element (Pulcini *et al.*, 2012, p. 7)–, a closer look at it reveals that it constitutes a more complex case. Note that the Eng. word *trampoline* (Sp. *cama elástica*) and the Sp. term *trampolín* (Eng. *diving board*) are false friends. Since the meaning alluded in the term under study is the English one (“a large piece of strong cloth held by springs in a frame”, CD), *trampolines jumping* turns out to be a combination of a semantic anglicism (which has adopted the meaning of an English paronym) and a non-adapted anglicism. Probably, it has been coined in Spanish as an abbreviation of the full English form *fitness trampoline jumping* (<https://www.we-go-wild.com/en/fitness-trampoline-exercises/>). DAD includes the forms *trampoline fitness* and *trampolining*, but not the one examined here.

- (10) la primera fase de los llamados trampolines jumping (*ABC*, 11/03/2021).

3.3 Non-adapted anglicisms

These are words or multi-word units borrowed from the English language without or with minor formal and semantic integration, so that they remain recognizably English in the RL (Pulcini *et al.*, 2012, p. 7). It is the most numerous category in this study, with 120 cases. In this section, a selection of the non-adapted technical or semi-technical loanwords within any field of sports has been examined, and as above mentioned, the rest may be consulted in the Appendix.

Many of these terms are also used in more general contexts, as is the case for *break, bunker, challenger, down, draft/drafting, drag, draw, drop, fade, foils, grip, leash, pick, pocket, refresher, spur, stretch, wedge, wing*, among others. It means that they are not exclusive of this specialized domain. However, this paper will focus on their technical uses in sports.

Some of the anglicisms collected show a connection between sports and animals, and are metaphorically structured. First, *agility* (present in DAD) refers to a sport which is practised by pets themselves.

- (11) especialistas veterinarios pueden recomendar realizar deportes específicos como el ‘agility’ que puede ser beneficioso para desarrollar las habilidades innatas de la mascota (*La Vanguardia*, 11/11/2020).

Second, *canicross* denotes a sport which, according to DAD (2021, p. 51), originated in Scandinavia and derives from mushing (see below). It consists of running with a dog tied at the waist. The term is a hybrid formation: Sp. *cani* (< Sp. *canino*) + Eng. *cross* (Sp. *carrera*) (DAD 2021: 51).

- (12) Con ella se dedicó a la práctica del ‘canicross’ (*El País*, 31/01/2021).

Third, *mushing* (present in DAD) makes reference to driving a dog sled (CD).

- (13) mushing, las carreras de trineo tirados por perros (*El Mundo*, 09/01/2021).

Although not involving animals in the actual practice of the sport, *bird dog* (not present in DAD) is used in American English to refer to

a stretching exercise in the posture of a four-legged dog. However, in British English it is still only a dog that you take hunting to collect the birds that you have shot. In Spanish press, it already seems to be in use with the American Eng. meaning, as example 14 shows.

- (14) Otro buen ejercicio es el bird dog (en cuadrupedia, estira un brazo y la pierna contraria hasta que queden paralelos al suelo) (*El País*, 23/09/2020).

Out of the anglicisms extracted in the chronological period under consideration, four of them are related to break dance, a practice which will be incorporated as an Olympic category from the 2024 Games onwards (europapress.es). The first two terms are *b-boy* and *b-girl*. See example 15. DAD records the latter, and also the form *b-boying*.

- (15) Ninguno de los ‘b-boys’ y ‘b-girls’ (así son conocidos los que bailan ‘breaking’) sabe qué música va a sonar cuando saltan a la pista (*El País*, 20/03/2021).

The third loanword is *breakdancer* (present in DAD), which is defined as ‘a person who does breakdancing’ (CD).

- (16) El breakdancer confesó que llegaron incluso a amenazarle (20 minutos, 12/02/2021).

Lastly, *breaking* (*break-dancing* and *breakdancing* are present in DAD) is an alternative name for the sport, as in example 17.

- (17) se ven obligados a referirse solo a este deporte como breaking (20 minutos, 12/02/2021).

Fatbike [Eng. *fat bike*] (not present in DAD) denotes “a bike with oversized tires. (...) They’re designed for a variety of terrain – from snow or sand to mud” (planetbikesguru.com).

- (18) La sensación fue parecida a montar una bicicleta ‘fatbike’ (*El País*, 01/03/2021).

GOAT –‘greatest of all time’– (not present in DAD) is mainly employed in US sport (CD) and is usually associated with the image of

the animal that happens to share the signifier with this abbreviation form. It is the only acronym recorded in this study.

- (19) ¿Quién va a ser el GOAT del tenis? ('greatest of all time') (*La Vanguardia*, 22/02/2021)

Several regular training exercises or routines which are not included in DAD (2021) appear in examples 20 – 25. They are *back lever*, *basic jump*, *front lever*, *full body*, *full planche*, *handstand*, *hip thrust*, *hollow rocks*, *jumping jacks*, *lunges* and *mountain climbers*.

- (20) Se caracteriza porque predomina el trabajo con peso corporal, y la fuerza y los recursos que se ganan se destinan a mejorar elementos muy artísticos como pueden ser el «handstand» (pino), «front lever», «back lever», «full planche» etc. (*ABC*, 26/09/2020).
- (21) Combinan ejercicios de alta intensidad (como *jumping jacks*, *mountain climbers* o *lunges*) con otros de baja que inciden en la fuerza (*El Mundo*, 14/10/2020).
- (22) Así, en las coreografías (...) es posible encontrar desde pasos básicos como el 'jogging', el 'step' o el 'basic jump' hasta otros más exigentes como los 'stompings' o el 'side to side' (*ABC*, 11/03/2021).
- (23) en ejercicios como la sentadilla o el *hip thrust* (20 minutos, 03/03/2021).
- (24) Descubre los 'hollow rocks', uno de los mejores ejercicios físicos para trabajar el abdomen (*El Confidencial*, 13/08/2020).
- (25) un entrenamiento full body (*El Confidencial*, 09/01/2021).

On the contrary, *crunch* is recorded in DAD. As for *core*, it is a term belonging to the field of anatomy ('the muscles around your pelvis,

hips, and abdomen that you use in most body movements’, COD), but when employed in a sports context it is connected to the exercises that can strengthen this muscular area (the form *core training* is enclosed in DAD).

(26) También los crunch, que se realizan tumbada boca arriba con las piernas flexionadas y las manos detrás de la cabeza (*El Confidencial*, 08/03/2021).

(27) se hace especial hincapié en las piernas y el abdomen, también la fuerza del core es clave (*El Confidencial*, 11/03/2021).

Leash (not present in DAD) is a leg rope or surfboard leash. “It is a urethane cord attached to the deck of a surfboard, down near the tail. It prevents the surfboard from being swept away by waves and stops runaway surfboards from hitting other surfers and swimmers” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Surfboard_leash).

(28) rompiese el leash (la correa que une la tabla de surf al tobillo) de su tabla (*20 minutos*, 24/02/2021).

Lucky loser (not present in DAD) is defined, according to the OED, as (a) (chiefly tennis) a competitor who loses in the qualifying round of a competition, but is given a place in the main draw after the withdrawal of another player through injury, illness, etc.; (b) a competitor, team, etc., who is not placed highly enough to qualify automatically for the later stages of a competition, but who gains entry by being one of the best-placed losers, or by playing a further knockout round.

(29) se enfrentará a la ‘lucky loser’ Margarita Gasparyan en la primera ronda (*La Vanguardia*, 06/02/2021).

Pipe (not present in DAD) is used in snow sports and refers to a place where freestyle skiers and snowboarders go to pull off tricks and practice aerial moves, as example 30 shows.

(30) Sin embargo, en un pipe que le vio ganar un oro en los X Games del año pasado, la emoción se mantuvo hasta el final (*El Mundo*, 14/03/2021).

Putt (present in DAD) is used in golf to refer to a stroke made on a putting green to cause the ball to roll into or near the hole. *Putter* is a stick with a short handle and metal end that is specially designed for putting (COD), as in example 31.

- (31) se trata de una técnica que lleva usando desde hace mucho y la que ahora ha vuelto a aferrarse (además de un productivo cambio de *putter*) para resurgir después de un tiempo de malos resultados y malas sensaciones sobre todo con el juego corto (*El País*, 05/10/2020).

Ruck (present in DAD) refers to a group of players in rugby who are all together around the ball when it is on the ground (COD). See example 32.

- (32) Sin tiempo para digerir el nuevo contexto, Fagerson era expulsado por entrar descontrolado al *ruck*—la zona de conquista del balón— y golpear a un rival cerca de la cabeza (*El País*, 13/02/2021).

Skipper (present in DAD) refers to the captain of a ship or boat, a sports team, or an aircraft (COD).

- (33) El skipper del Emirates Team New Zealand, Peter Burling, fue pragmático acerca de las condiciones (*ABC*, 14/03/2021).

Smash (present in DAD) is employed in tennis and volleyball to refer to a powerful downward hit that sends the ball forcefully over the net.

- (34) Después mandaron los saques hasta que con 3-3 Rafa falló otro ‘smash’ (*El Confidencial*, 17/02/2021).

Tackling (present in DAD) is frequently used in football and hockey to refer to the action of catching and knocking down someone who is running. A *tackle* is a person who frequently carries out this action in a game.

- (35) El tackle izquierdo Kolton Miller, el guardia izquierdo Denzelle Good, el centro Rodney Hudson y el guardia derecho Gabe Jackson salieron de la lista de coronavirus (*EFE*, 25/10/2020).

Tanking (not present in DAD) is a strategy used by NBA that consists of NBA teams that purposely lose in the short term to obtain higher picks in the NBA draft that (they hope) will help them win in the long term, as in example 36.

- (36) Cuando perder en la NBA es la mejor opción los peores equipos hacen ‘tanking’, dejarse llevar para elegir luego a los mejores universitarios (*ABC*, 24/03/2021).

Tee (present in DAD) is frequently used in golf to refer to a short plastic stick with a cup-shaped top on which a golf ball is put to be hit, or the area where this is used to start the play for each hole. See example 37.

- (37) De 2019 a 2020, el aumento en terreno ganado desde el ‘tee’ fue de 2,4 metros en el circuito estadounidense y de 5,3 en el europeo (*El País*, 02/02/2021).

Table 2 (see Appendix) compiles the rest of technical/semi-technical anglicisms and anglicized phrases with their examples of real use in context.

4 Functions of anglicisms

Up to now, some studies have focused on the pragmatic functions fulfilled by anglicisms when employed in some contexts in Spanish. González Cruz and Rodríguez Medina (2011) examined, specifically, the youth sociolect in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain). After having explored anglicisms and pseudoanglicisms employed in Spanish TV and radio humorous programmes, Rodríguez Medina (2004) concluded that these English lexical units were used with expressive and comic purposes. In order to contribute to this particular area of study, and following Rodríguez González’s (1996) categorization of anglicisms according to their pragmatic functions, this section illustrates these uses in the news with some of the examples from the collection of English lexical items under consideration:

4.1 Ideational function

Also called “referential” by Jacobson and Hymes (in Rodríguez González, 1996), it is based on Halliday’s model, and anglicisms that belong to this type are “borrowings that fill in a gap of the language, since there are no alternative expressions when they first appear” (Rodríguez González, 1996, p.110). Due to their degree of speciality, they are used in English in the RL. Some examples (see Appendix) are terms such as *break* in tennis, *bunker* and *putter* in golf, *flanker*, *ruck* and *touchdown* in rugby, *pitcher* in baseball, *tight end* in American football, *curling* in ice, *pit lane* in motor racing, and *tackling* in hockey and football. In all these cases, these sports come from English-speaking countries, where additionally they are quite popular, and no equivalent terms have emerged in Spanish. Similar is the case of *biker*, since it is used to refer to a person who rides a bicycle or a motorbike, whereas in Spanish two words are employed (*ciclista* for a bicycle rider and *motociclista/motero/motorista* for a motorbike rider). The following example 38 illustrates in context the ideational function of the term *break*, which in tennis is defined as to win a game as the receiving player or team, thereby breaking serve. In Spanish, there is not a specific term that expresses this concept with accuracy in this domain. Therefore, in this case, the loanword fills in a language gap in Spanish.

- (38) [...] que aprovechó un break en el primer parcial para llevarse el set y empezar con buen tino en el segundo (*ABC*, 11/03/2021).

Some other anglicisms such as *trekking* and *hiking* (in Sp. *senderismo*) provide slight nuances in meaning such as the difficulty and the paths for which it is developed. Particularly, *hiking* is defined by CD as the sporting or leisure activity of going for long, often strenuous, walks in the country. The Spanish term does not contain this difference, as example 39 shows.

- (39) la herramienta perfecta para ‘hiking’ largos y veloces (*El País*, 01/03/2021).

4.2 Interpersonal or expressive function

The interpersonal or expressive function is generally fulfilled by terms that contain connotations such as irony, contempt, snobbery or prestige. These positive or negative associations are related to the sociolect, to many contextually related factors, and also to the specific characteristics of the topic being talked about or the nature of the concept being referred to. Thus, many of these words have Spanish equivalents, but journalists and news reporters still choose the English term to express these connotations, usually positive and associated with prestige, professionalism, and even snobbery. Some examples excerpted from the sample are *draw* (in Sp. *empate*), *pick* (in Sp. *elegir/elección*), *runner* (in Sp. *corredor/a*), *soccer* (in Sp. *fútbol*), *stretch* (in Sp. *estirar*), *surfer* (in Sp. *surfero/a*, *surfista*), *training camp* (in Sp. *campo de entrenamiento*), *trainer* (in Sp. *entrenador*), and *workout* (in Sp. *entrenamiento*). Some English expressions collected in this sample that also fulfil this function are *full planche* (in Sp. *plancha completa*) and *handstand* (in Sp. *pino*).

We will provide a contextualized example with the term *pick*, which is defined by Collins Dictionary as ‘a person, thing, etc, that is chosen first or preferred’. In Spanish the domain of sport also uses *seleccionado*, but the journalist still prefers to choose the English loanword *pick*. Probably, the anglicized lexical item is opted for because it provides a sense of prestige and professionalism, as example 40 demonstrates.

- (40) Pívot de Memphis de 19 años. Más allá de la decisión de traspasar la elección o no, suena al ‘pick’ más lógico (*El Mundo*, 18/11/2020).

4.3 Textual function

Journalists and news reporters may also want to present a more simplified version of a term following the principle of the economy of the language. There are English words which are simple as opposed to their long and more complex Spanish versions. This is the case for borrowings such as *snorkeling* (in Sp. *nadar usando gafas, tubo y aletas*), *kettlebell* (in Sp. *pesas rusas*) or *pace car* (in Sp. *coche de seguridad*).

The following example 41 reports the usage of *snorkeling*, which is defined as the activity of swimming while using a snorkel (COD), as a good illustration of economy of language.

- (41) [...] se fomenten formas de bajo impacto como el *snorkeling*, el buceo, una excursión en kayak o un paseo por la costa (*El Mundo*, 12/03/2021).

In this section, we have covered a wide variety of uses of anglicisms with different purposes which range from sounding cool, prestigious or professional, filling a word gap, or following the principle of economy of language. Due to space limitations, this paper includes just a few commented examples of the pragmatic functions of some of the compiled anglicisms.

5 Discussion

This piece of research provides updated data of the current uses of English sports-related technical/semi-technical terms in the written language of the European Spanish press. Terminology associated to a broad spectrum of specific sports –such as golf, basketball, rugby, cycling, etc.– has been collected. On some occasions, a given anglicism is employed in two different sports games, as is the case for *smash* (tennis and volleyball) and *tackling* (football and hockey).

While some terms have no connection to the rest of borrowings, many of them can be grouped according to certain parameters. Three anglicisms are characterized by linking sports and animals using metaphorical structures (*agility*, *canicross* and *mushing*). There are four terms related to break dance (*b-boys*, *b-girls*, *breakdancer* and *breaking*), a practice which will be present in the Olympic Games from 2024 onwards. Considering regular training exercises or routines, the following eleven anglicisms have been identified: *back lever*, *basic jump*, *front lever*, *full body*, *full planche*, *handstand*, *hip thrust*, *hollow rocks*, *jumping jacks*, *lunges* and *mountain climbers*.

Admittedly, and taking into account that Observatorio Lázaro only picks up those lexical items whose orthographic and morphological form corresponds to that of an English word, the overwhelming majority of the borrowings analyzed in this piece of research are non-adapted English lexical items. However, the adapted terms *coastering*, *down*, and *speed ski*

as well as the false anglicisms *paddle surf*, *car-cross*, *fast bike*, *start lap*, *sparring*, *supercrack* and *trampolines jumping* must also be underlined.

When it comes to the pragmatic functions of these English lexical units, the brief analysis reveals that three different functions –namely, referential or ideational, interpersonal or expressive, and textual– respond to news reporters’ and journalists’ intentions. The choice of these terms is not the result of a coincidence, but they intend to fulfil a particular function in the piece of news and in the way to attract the attention of the reader. In this paper, it is necessary to highlight that the border between technical and semi-technical terms is frequently quite blurred.

Regarding typographical marks employed by news reporters, different elements point to the foreign nature of the words recorded in this study. The use of simple inverted commas can be underscored as the most frequent resource in the collected examples. Furthermore, Latin quotation marks and italics are occasionally resorted to. Nevertheless, numerous English lexical items appear without any mark, which comes across as an indication of their integration into the Spanish specialized field of sports.

Considering whether the anglicism is accompanied by a Spanish equivalent or a brief explanation of its meaning in the recipient language, it must be claimed that, whereas numerous terms are clarified by means of these translations, many others are not complemented with this linguistic resource. The latter case seems to reveal the familiarity of the readers with this foreign technical/semitechnical terminology; they can, therefore, understand it when employed in the original language – or, at least, that is what the journalists presuppose.

6 Conclusions

This paper has presented updated data on a specific field of Spanish language: sports. It has offered a deep analysis that does not merely describe facts, but it intends to go further by reporting on the reasons why these English lexical items are used, classifying the terms into the type of anglicism each of them belongs to and providing explanations on a variety of aspects concerning the usage of these foreign words in Spanish language co-texts. A collection of 130 English lexical items has been analyzed and categorized into non-adapted, adapted, and false English borrowings (Pulcini *et al.*, 2012). Every anglicism has been looked up in DAD, the most recent dictionary of sports-related English lexical items in Spanish.

Thus, as research in the sphere of borrowing is always an incomplete task, the present paper can complement DAD up to March 2021.

In this study, an overall quantitative as well as an in-depth qualitative and descriptive analysis has been offered in relation to the use of technical/semitechnical anglicisms in the Spanish specialized field of sports. After a detailed examination of these English lexical units, it has been confirmed that the pervasive influence exerted by this donor language on the recipient tongue under consideration remains in full force and effect nowadays. Results show that this impact affects the vocabulary of a wide variety of sports games and exercises, as can be seen not just in specialized newspapers devoted to this domain but also in the generalist press that has been consulted in this study.

The use of foreign terms is a strategy frequently employed in journalistic language not only to draw the attention of the reader, but also to offer a sense of professionalism on the part of the writer. English is unquestionably associated with values of prestige; therefore, the use of these anglicisms responds to this attempt by the journalist. As Rodríguez Segura (1999) asserted, whenever they are employed, anglicisms always meet a particular need on the part of the speaker, that is, there is always some reason for the use of an anglicism.

Despite its limitations, this piece of research allows linguists and language users in general to become more aware of the growing tendency to employ English loanwords in their everyday use of the language when they refer to sports and sports-related activities. Furthermore, since this study provides evidence of a global language such as Spanish, the findings presented in this paper could possibly be extended to other Spanish varieties in a more international context, namely Latin-American countries. Future research could also shed some more light by means of comparative analyses that could reveal an increasing or decreasing tendency to the employment of anglicisms and anglicized phrases in the area of sports.

Author declaration

Luján-García has contributed 50% of sections introduction, methodology, findings and conclusions, in addition to 100% of section functions of anglicisms. Núñez Nogueroles has contributed 50% of sections introduction, methodology, findings and conclusions in addition to 100% of section discussion. The compilation of the sample in Table 2 (in the appendix) has also been worked 50% by both authors.

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Appendix A – Non-adapted technical and semi-technical Anglicisms used in the field of sports (not included in the section ‘Findings’)

	Anglicism and anglicized phrases	Present in DAD	Example of use in context	Source	Date
1	<i>Aquafitness</i> : a keep-fit regime in which exercises are performed standing up in a swimming pool (CD).	yes	Sustitúyelos por ejercicios hipopresivos, aquagym, aquafitness, pilates y yoga	<i>EFE</i>	09/02/2021
2	<i>Beach break</i> : a beach break is a surf-able wave that is breaking onto a beach (https://www.degree33surfboards.com/blogs/gettin-pitted/14071029-the-differences-between-beach-breaks-point-breaks-and-reef-breaks).	yes	La mencionada playa ofrece varios picos tipo beach break, donde las olas rompen sobre un fondo de arena	<i>20 minutos</i>	24/02/2021
3	<i>Bike park</i> : an area where bikers can train with their bikes.	no	Son perfectos para los entornos urbanos, bike parks y pump tracks	<i>20 Minutos</i>	25/10/2020
4	<i>Biker</i> : people who ride around on bicycles or motorbikes, usually in groups (CD).	yes	Montero, otro conocido y hábil ‘biker’, también pionero de la bici de montaña en España	<i>El Confidencial</i>	26/01/2021
5	<i>Boardercross</i> : also snowboardcross. Competition in which four to six competitors race down a course.	yes	el flamante campeón del mundo de boardercross	<i>El Confidencial</i>	12/02/2021

6	<i>Bodybuilding</i> : the activity of doing special exercises regularly in order to make your muscles grow bigger (CD).	body building	Y la gerundense Isa Fontbona, practicante de bodybuilding	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	20/10/2020
7	<i>Boogie boarder / Boogie-boarding</i> : synonym of bodyboarder. A surfboard that is shorter and blunter than the standard board and on which the surfer lies rather than stands (CD).	boogy	“Un ‘boogie boarder’ [persona que utiliza una pequeña table de surf para coger olas] en (...)”	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	10/02/2021
8	<i>Break</i> : in tennis, to win a game as the receiving player or team, thereby breaking serve.	yes	que aprovechó un break en el primer parcial para llevarse el set y empezar con buen tino en el segundo	<i>ABC</i>	11/03/2021
9	<i>Bungee jumping</i> : jump from a high place such as a bridge or cliff with a long piece of strong elastic cord tied around their ankle connecting them to the bridge or cliff (CD).	yes	un sitio para hacer puenting o ‘bungee jumping’	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	05/12/2020
10	<i>Bunker</i> : in golf, if you bunker a shot, you hit your ball into the bunker (CD).	yes	Repitió salida desde el bunker, esta vez con destino al green, en el que necesitó dos putts para embocar y acabar el hoyo con diez golpes (+7)	<i>El Mundo</i>	15/11/2020

11	<i>Challenger</i> : someone who competes with you for a position or title that you already have, for example being a sports champion (CD).	yes	Todavía trabaja su tenis en los torneos «challengers»	<i>ABC</i>	16/02/2021
12	<i>Chessboxing</i> : a sport in which participants contest alternating rounds of chess and boxing, of four and two minutes respectively (CD).	no	El boxeador que sabía jugar al ajedrez: “El ‘chessboxing’ destruye estereotipos”	<i>El Mundo</i>	28/07/2020
13	<i>Clinch</i> : the position two people are in when they are holding each other tightly in their arms, when fighting (COD).	yes	un poco abrumado por los golpes de su rival, llevó la pelea al ‘clinch’ para asegurar el asalto con su control	<i>El Confidencial</i>	14/03/2021
14	<i>Cross training</i> : training in two or more sports to improve performance (CD).	yes	tanto el Cross training como el CrossFit, ambos entrenamientos funcionales	<i>20 minutos</i>	07/03/2021
15	<i>Curling</i> : a game played on ice, in which heavy stones with handles are slid towards a target (CD).	yes	deportes como el esquí, el patinaje sobre hielo, el ‘curling’ o el ‘bobsleigh’	<i>El País</i>	11/02/2021

16	<i>Defensive back</i> : a defender positioned off the line of scrimmage for the purpose of covering and tackling runners who elude linemen and linebackers (CD).	defensive end	Jones llegó a jugar tres amistosos como <i>defensive back</i>	<i>El Mundo</i>	26/12/2020
17	<i>Draft</i> : the system by which sports teams in the US choose new young players at the beginning of each season (COD).	yes	Tras cumplir su misión, fue elegido como ‘número dos’ del ‘draft’ de 1993 por los Sixers	<i>El Mundo</i>	18/03/2021
18	<i>Drafting</i> : the practice of riding in the slipstream close behind someone’s rear wheel, thus greatly reducing the effort you need to expend keeping at their speed (https://www.theguardian.com/environment/bike-blog/2011/aug/25/cycling-commuter-drafting-etiquette).	yes	En la bici [sin drafting pese a ser un olímpico, normas anti coronavirus], mantuve el tipo	<i>El Mundo</i>	18/09/2020
19	<i>Drag</i> : resistance to the movement that is experienced by something that is moving through air or through a fluid (CD). Used in car races.	yes	Dichos apéndices guían esos flujos hacia el exterior para reducir las turbulencias y el drag	<i>El Confidencial</i>	18/03/2021

20	<i>Draw</i> : if two people or teams draw, they have the same number of points or goals at the end of the game (CD).	yes	golpes al draw y también al fade que es como he jugado siempre	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	17/09/2020
21	<i>Drives</i> : if a player drives a ball somewhere, they kick or hit it there with a lot of force. In golf, a drive is the first stroke a player makes from the tee (CD).	yes	amenaza con pegar <i>drives</i> por encima de las 400 yardas	<i>El Mundo</i>	11/11/2020
22	<i>Drop</i> : to throw, shoot, hit, kick, or roll (a ball, puck, etc.) through or into a basket, hole, or other goal (CD).	yes	pero el español la neutralizó con saque abierto y <i>drop</i>	<i>El Mundo</i>	19/09/2020
23	<i>Drop shot</i> : in tennis, a softly-played return that drops abruptly after clearing the net, intended to give an opponent no chance of reaching the ball and usually achieved by imparting backspin (CD).	yes	En el segundo juego se retó al rival con un ‘drop shot’	<i>EFE</i>	16/03/2021
24	<i>E-bike</i> : a bicycle that can be powered by electricity as well as by pedalling (CD).	no	ya se encuentran patinetes eléctricos o e-bikes con un toque de distinción	<i>20 minutos</i>	14/03/2021
25	<i>Fade</i> : in golf, the path of a ball that is faded or that slices slightly (CD).	yes	golpes al draw y también al fade que es como he jugado siempre	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	17/09/2020

26	<i>Fast lane</i> : the part of the road where the vehicles that are travelling fastest go (CD).	no	piden turno en la línea rápida, el conocido como 'fast lane'	20 minutos	15/08/2020
27	<i>Field goal</i> : in football, a field goal is a score of three points that is gained by kicking the ball through the opponent's goalposts above the crossbar (CD).	yes	Kansas City fue el primero en anotar tras un 'field goal' (0-3)	20 minutos	08/02/2021
28	<i>Flanker</i> : in rugby, a wing forward. In American football, an offensive back who takes a position closer to the sideline than the rest of the team (CD).	yes	creía que podía ser 'flanker' en la NFL	20 minutos	08/02/2021
29	<i>Foils</i> : the art or practice of fencing with this weapon, points being made by touching the trunk of the opponent's body with the tip of the weapon (CD).	no	estar sobre los foils significó la diferencia entre liderar y perder	ABC	15/03/2021
30	<i>Freerider</i> : a person who is specialized in the sport free ride.	Free-ride: Surf style on snow or skying in steep surfaces	Si un 'freerider' se cae y pierde algo de material, tendrá un cero	El País	30/01/2021

31	<i>Free runner</i> : people who move quickly around buildings and objects in a city while performing jumps and other skilful movements (COD).	no	free runner Johan Tonnoir, que recorre sus instalaciones a golpe de saltos y acrobacias	<i>El País</i>	29/07/2020
32	<i>Freestyler</i> : a person who specializes or competes in a freestyle sporting event (CD).	yes	es más fácil hacerse 'freestyler' que jugar al fútbol	<i>El Confidencial</i>	02/01/2021
33	<i>Front runner</i> : in a competition or contest, the front-runner is the person who seems most likely to win it (CD).	no	'front runner' como una veterana	<i>El País</i>	05/03/2021
34	<i>Full back</i> : in rugby or football, a full-back is a defending player whose position is towards the goal which their team is defending (CD).	fullback	un 'full back' de la NFL	<i>El País</i>	12/10/2020
35	<i>Game</i> : it is a part of a match, for example in tennis or bridge, consisting of a fixed number of points (CD).	yes	el último 'game' del partido, Djokovic tropezó	<i>20 minutos</i>	06/09/2020
36	<i>Gennaker</i> : a type of sail used for downwind sailing (CD).	no	Anoche estuve con un gennaker pequeño con un rizo, la brisa subía y bajaba	<i>ABC</i>	23/01/2021

37	<i>Geocaching</i> : a game in which the object is to identify and find items deposited by other players, using GPS navigation (CD).	no	de orientación en kayak, 'geocaching', hípica, parapente	<i>El País</i>	21/08/2020
38	<i>Grip</i> : the style or manner of grasping an object, such as a tennis racket (CD)	yes	la raqueta, siempre con los 'grips' [empuñaduras] más finos posible	<i>El País</i>	07/02/2021
39	<i>Ground and pound</i> : a fighting style, primarily in mixed martial arts, in which one pins one's opponent and then strikes him or her repeatedly.	no	es un devastador golpeador en el 'ground and pound'.	<i>El Confidencial</i>	21/02/2021
40	<i>Half-pipe</i> : a structure with a U-shaped cross-section, used in performing stunts in skateboarding, snowboarding, etc (CD).	yes	en la Copa del Mundo de 'half-pipe'	<i>El Confidencial</i>	16/02/2021
41	<i>Handbike</i> : three-wheeled devices configured with a pedaling system that is operated using the hands and arms rather than the legs and feet.	no	para desarrollar así una <i>handbike</i> de montaña	<i>El Diario</i>	02/02/2021

42	<i>Head coach</i> : a head coach, senior coach, or manager is a professional at training and developing athletes.	no	El <i>head coach</i> de los Patriots	20 minutos	12/01/2021
43	<i>High side</i> : a type of motorcycle crash where the motorcycle tire loses, then rapidly regains traction, thus throwing the rider violently up, over, and off the motorcycle as the motorcycle spins off on its own trajectory.	no	El high side de Álex Márquez	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	14/11/2020
44	<i>High rake</i> : a high-rake car has a more visible difference in angle between the front of the car and the rear, where the diffuser is jacked up considerably and the front tray of the floor runs very close to the ground.	no	Newey fue el precursor en la Fórmula 1 del 'high rake'	<i>El Confidencial</i>	24/02/2021
45	<i>Hiking</i> : the sporting or leisure activity of going for long, often strenuous, walks in the country (CD).	no	la herramienta perfecta para 'hiking' largos y veloces	<i>El País</i>	01/03/2021

46	<i>Instant replay</i> : the reshewing of an action, as of a play in a sports contest, often in slow motion, immediately after it has been recorded on videotape (CD).	yes	el anuncio de que el instant replay iba a resolver las polémicas	<i>El Mundo</i>	24/01/2021
47	<i>Kettlebell</i> : gymnastics, weightlifting (CD).	yes	llevando el disco, la kettlebell o el balón medicinal de un lado a otro del cuerpo	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	08/02/2021
48	<i>Long lap Lap</i> : in a race, a competitor completes a lap when they have gone round a course once (CD).	no	una sanción en la última vuelta de tres segundos por no hacer el ‘long lap’	<i>El Confidencial</i>	20/09/2020
49	<i>Master trainer</i> : it is another name for a personal trainer at many fitness facilities. (https://www.sportsrec.com/428902-master-trainers-vs-personal-trainer.html).	no	‘master trainer’ de ‘Peak Pilates’ en España	<i>ABC</i>	13/03/2021
50	<i>Match race</i> : (chiefly U.S.) a race, esp. a horse race, run according to competition rules (OED).	yes	La novena regata fue sublime, el mejor duelo de ‘match race’ visto hasta ahora	<i>El Mundo</i>	16/03/2021

51	<i>One club man</i> : a player who spends their entire playing/ managing career with the same club (https://alvinalmazov.com/soccer-eng/one-club-man/).	no	pocas ganas tiene ahora de acabar su carrera donde la empezó, de ser un <i>one club man</i> como suspiraba la hinchada azulgrana	<i>El País</i>	01/02/2021
52	<i>Pace car</i> : a car sent on to the track during a race to control the pace of competitors in temporarily hazardous conditions (OED).	yes	Sage Karam rozó el muro de la curva 4, el punto más crítico del óvalo, pero todo se quedó en un susto sin necesidad de que saliera el ‘pace car’, el coche de seguridad	<i>20 minutos</i>	21/08/2020
53	<i>Passing shot</i> : an occasion when you successfully hit the ball past the other player in tennis (COD).	yes	El passing shot de Daniil Medvedev se va fuera	<i>ABC</i>	21/02/2021
54	<i>Personal trainer</i> : someone whose job is to help you become stronger and healthier by deciding which exercises you should do and showing you how to do them (COD).	yes	La grasa no se quema de manera localizada, tal como explica Xus Sáez, personal trainer de Be You Fitness Experiences	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	08/02/2021

55	<i>Pit lane:</i> (Motor Racing) a side road parallel to a course which leads into and out of the pits (OED).	yes	en Yas Marina, donde ayer debió esperar dos horas hasta la decisión de los comisarios, que dejaron sin castigo su maniobra en el <i>pit-lane</i>	<i>El Mundo</i>	14/12/2020
56	<i>Pick:</i> a person, thing, etc, that is chosen first or preferred (CD).	no	Pívot de Memphis de 19 años. Más allá de la decisión de traspasar la elección o no, suena al ‘pick’ más lógico	<i>El Mundo</i>	18/11/2020
57	<i>Pick and roll:</i> (Basketball) a manoeuvre in which a player performs a legitimate block or screen on a defender before moving behind the defender to receive a pass from a teammate (OED).	yes	Es bueno en el pick and roll pero puede sufrir con el estilo de campo abierto de los Warriors	<i>El Mundo</i>	18/11/2020
58	<i>Pitcher:</i> in baseball, the pitcher is the person who throws the ball to the batter, who tries to hit it (CD).	yes	CC Sabathia es uno de los ‘pitchers’ más reconocibles de la historia del béisbol	<i>20 minutos</i>	13/02/2021
59	<i>Playmaking:</i> the initiating of offensive plays in sports (CD).	playmaker	como si cada vez fuera más difícil distinguir unas de otras en un molde uniforme donde playmaking y shot creation lo justifican todo	<i>El Confidencial</i>	04/03/2021

60	<i>Pocket</i> : (American Football and Canadian Football) a shielded area formed by blockers from which a player attempts to pass (OED).	yes	La defensa de Tampa Bay maniató a Mahomes, al que obligó a ganar yardas saliendo del <i>pocket</i> y cuyo brazo tampoco funcionó como se esperaba	<i>ABC</i>	08/02/2021
61	<i>Raft / Rafting</i> : rafting is the sport of travelling down a river on a raft (CD).	yes	La palabra rafting procede del inglés raft, que significa balsa	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	17/07/2020
62	<i>Rally raid</i> : (also known as off road or cross country rallying) a form of long distance off road racing that takes place over several days, often in extreme environments (https://www.bowlermotors.com/our-services/bowler-racing/rally-raid/).	yes	la competición –en el asfalto o en la tierra de los rally-raids– se ha convertido en el mejor banco de pruebas para evaluar el rendimiento de sus productos	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	21/10/2020
63	<i>Refresher</i> : an activity that refreshes one’s skills or knowledge (MD).	no	Ya en la semana de entrenamientos de las 500 Millas, ni siquiera podía salir de boxes por otra avería en la sesión de novatos y ‘refreshers’	<i>El Confidencial</i>	20/08/2020

64	<i>(Electronic)</i> <i>Road book</i> : a tablet which has replaced the paper road book –for elite pilots– at the Dakar Rally (https://es.motorsport.com/dakar/news/roadbook-digital-funcionamiento-dakar-que-es/4928484/).	yes	dificultad para interpretar el nuevo libro de ruta electrónico del ‘raid’. Nos ha costado entender la filosofía nueva del ‘road book’ y lo hemos pagado	<i>El Confidencial</i>	08/01/2021
65	<i>Rulebook</i> : a rule book is a book containing the official rules for a particular game, job, or organization (CD).	no	“De acuerdo con el Grand Slam Rulebook y atendiendo a la acción de golpear intencionada y peligrosamente la bola imprudentemente o sin tener en cuenta las consecuencias (...)”	<i>El País</i>	07/09/2020
66	<i>Runner / Running</i> : a runner is a person who runs, especially for sport or pleasure	yes	Europeísta, feminista, liberal en lo económico, disciplinada ‘runner’ y con el ritmo suficiente como para tocar la batería	<i>El Mundo</i>	26/01/2021

67	<i>Running back:</i> (American Football) an offensive back, usually one of a pair, responsible primarily for rushing the ball; halfback or fullback (CD).	yes	El running back de los Bucs ha logrado anotar un touchdown nada más salir del descanso	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	08/02/2021
68	<i>Sandbagging</i> Sandbag: to underperform in a race or competition in order to gain an unfair handicap or other advantage (OED).	no	No se trata de marear la perdiz, el famoso ‘sandbagging’ del argot carrerista	<i>El Confidencial</i>	16/03/2021
69	<i>Snorkeling:</i> the activity of swimming while using a snorkel (COD).	yes	se fomenten formas de bajo impacto como el <i>snorkeling</i> , el buceo, una excursión en kayak o un paseo por la costa	<i>El Mundo</i>	12/03/2021
70	<i>Snowboard cross:</i> in snowboarding: a competition in which multiple participants race simultaneously on a downhill course characterized by extreme variations in terrain; = boardercross (OED).	yes	Lucas Eguibar (San Sebastián, 27 años), campeón del mundo de ‘snowboard cross’ (una competición de velocidad en nieve sobre una tabla)	<i>El País</i>	14/02/2021
71	<i>Snowboarder:</i> a person who rides a snowboard; a participant in snowboarding (OED).	yes	Muere un ‘snowboarder’ tras un accidente en una pista cerrada al público de Sierra Nevada	<i>20 minutos</i>	28/01/2021

72	<i>Soccer</i> : the game of football as played under the rules of the Football Association (OED).	yes	es llevar la disputa por la ‘Orejona’ a Estados Unidos para fomentar el mercado del ‘soccer’ allí	<i>20 minutos</i>	26/02/2021
73	<i>Stretch</i> : the act of straightening your body, your arms, or your legs so that they are as long as possible (COD).	stretching	fue suplantado por el ‘stretch’, que en la persecución a los atacantes abiertos convierte las defensas en acordeones	<i>El Confidencial</i>	04/03/2021
74	<i>Striker / Striking</i> : it is a type of class that combines Muay Thai and Western Boxing (https://www.ufcgymchile.cl/clases/striking/).	striker	Tanto en el ‘striking’ como en la lucha de agarre el español fue dominante	<i>El Confidencial</i>	11/10/2020
75	<i>Surfer</i> : a person who rides on a wave on a special board (COD).	no	Esta vez, el hito lleva la firma de un joven con aspecto de ‘surfer’ que va consolidándose en la planta noble del circuito	<i>El País</i>	18/02/2021
76	<i>Tight-end</i> : (American Football) an offensive end (...) who lines up close to the tackle; the position occupied by this player (OED).	yes	Mahomes encuentra a Travis Kelce pero el tight-end no consigue atrapar el balón cuando estaba en una situación idónea	<i>El Mundo</i>	08/02/2021

77	<i>Touchdown:</i> in rugby and American football, a touchdown is when a team scores points by taking the ball over the opposition's goal line (CD).	yes	Hizo tres pases de touchdown, dos con recepciones de Gronkowski	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	08/02/2021
78	<i>Trail / Trail runner</i> <i>Trail running:</i> the sport or activity of running along trails (= paths through a countryside, mountain, or forest area) (COD).	trail	“¿No querías ser trail runner? Pues te jodes”	<i>20 minutos</i>	26/02/2021
79	<i>Trainer:</i> a person who teaches skills to people or animals and prepares them for a job, activity, or sport (COD).	yes	Melo trabajó entonces a destajo, entre Nueva York y Los Ángeles, con el trainer que mejor lo conocía, Alex Bazzell	<i>El Confidencial</i>	13/11/2020
80	<i>Training camp:</i> (for soldiers or sports players) an organized period of training at a particular place.	no	un problema silenciado por el cuerpo técnico ya en el training camp de Louisiana durante las primeras pruebas de juego real	<i>El Confidencial</i>	13/11/2020
81	<i>Trekker:</i> a person travelling a long distance, esp. on foot; spec. a rambler or hiker (OED).	yes	En 1977, el número de turistas de montaña ('trekkers') que llegaron a Nepal fue de 21.919	<i>El Confidencial</i>	04/02/2021

82	<i>Tubeless</i> : having no tube or tubes (OED).	no	cada vez es más popular la opción de montar cubiertas sin cámara (tubeless), sobre todo en ciclismo de montaña	<i>La Vanguardia</i>	16/02/2021
83	<i>Wakesurfing</i> : wakesurfing is riding a board behind a boat by a towing vessel ((https://prosurfing.com/learn-to-surf/wakesurfing-a-step-by-step-guide-for-beginners.html)).	no	La última de Piqué: sube un vídeo practicando 'wakesurfing' con Shakira y sus hijos	<i>20 minutos</i>	14/07/2020
84	<i>Wedge</i> : a golf club with a wedge-shaped head, used for lofting the ball at approach shots, or (...) out of a bunker, etc. Also, a shot made with a wedge (OED).	yes	pero hasta el hierro 8, probablemente más en el 9 y con el 'wedge', la bola se lanza un poco más abajo, con más efecto	<i>El País</i>	25/02/2021
85	<i>Wing</i> : in football and similar games: The position of the forwards on either side of the centre; a player or players occupying this position (OED).	yes	de 'switching' han desaparecido y las posiciones tendido a concentrarse en los 'wings' como un estándar de fábrica	<i>El Confidencial</i>	04/03/2021

86	<i>Wrestler / Wrestling:</i> a wrestler is someone who wrestles as a sport, usually for money (CD)	wrestling	En concreto, un 'wrestler' tiene 15 veces más posibilidades de morir de un infarto que cualquier otro ciudadano	<i>El Confidencial</i>	30/09/2020
87	<i>Workout:</i> a period of physical exercise or training (CD).	no	Partiendo de la base de que una persona quiera y necesite tonificar su cuerpo, "puede valer un fullbody o un workout (...)"	<i>20 minutos</i>	23/02/2021

Source: own elaboration.